

view of the numerous applications of acid hydrazides, their determination is of immense scope and value.

Since the choice of indicator solution did not affect the results of the visual titrations, for brevity only one set of results (with diphenylamine) is recorded in Table 1. In potentiometric titrations, a sharp drop in potential of the order of 180-290 mV per 0.05 ml of the hydrazide solution is observed at the equivalence point when modified-calomel electrode is used and 200-280 mV with the antimony reference electrode. The potentials at the inflection points are 980-590 mV (modified calomel) and 660-380 mV (antimony electrode). The results recorded in Table 1 show that the overall standard deviation calculated from the pooled data of all the visual and potentiometric (modified-calomel electrode) titrations performed with 4 mg (the amount corresponds to the theoretical end-point) of each compound are 0.034 and 0.030 respectively. For 10 mg samples they are 0.056 and 0.052 respectively.

The proposed method is based on the oxidation of phenylhydrazides with a two-electron change per hydrazino group. This may correspond to their oxidation to diazonium compounds.

That phenylhydrazides could be oxidatively converted to diazonium compounds is already known⁷.

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Complexes of Cerium(III) with Benzoic Acid, Protocatechuic Acid and Salicylic Acid : A Polarographic Study

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IN previous communications the complexes of Pr(III) and Nd(III)^{1,2} with benzoic acid, protocatechuic acid and salicylic acid by polarographic technique were reported^{1,2}. However, the literature

is silent about the study of complexes of Ce(III) with these ligands at a DME. The present paper deals with the composition and stability constants of Ce(III) with benzoic acid, protocatechuic acid and salicylic acid respectively by Lingane and Deford-Hume treatment of the observed polarographic data.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR/BDH grade. Ce(III) (0.01 M) solution was prepared by dissolving a calculated quantity of $CeCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ (Fluka AG, Switzerland) in conductivity water and was standardised by EDTA method³. Potassium chloride and gelatin solutions were prepared in double distilled water. The stock solutions (0.1 M) of sodium benzoate, protocatechuic acid and potassium salicylate were prepared in carbon-dioxide-free double distilled water.

A preliminary experimental set was prepared by keeping overall concentrations of metal ion, potassium chloride and gelatin at 1 mM, 1.0 M and 0.01 % respectively. While in other sets in addition to the above metal ion, supporting electrolyte and maximum suppressor, the concentration of ligand in each case was varied from 0.25 mM to 30.0 mM. The ionic strength was fixed at $I=1.0$ by adding requisite amount of potassium chloride. The pH of the test solutions was kept at 3.0 ± 0.02 by necessary addition of hydrochloric acid and was measured with an Elico digital pH meter (Model LI-120).

An automatic pen recording polarograph CIC (Baroda, India) was used for recording polarograms. Potentials were measured against saturated calomel electrode. The capillary had the following characteristics; $m=2.13$ mg/sec, $t=3.0$ sec/drop ($m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.323$ mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/6}) in 1.0 M potassium chloride at 35 cm effective height of the mercury column. Pure nitrogen gas was passed through the test solutions before recording the polarograms. All the measurements were made at room temperature, $26 \pm 1^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

Ce(III) gives a well defined, reversible three electron reduction wave in 1.0 M potassium chloride in presence of 0.01% gelatin at pH $3.0 \pm 0.02^{4,5}$. The reduction of Ce(III) and of its complexes with all the three ligands under study were found to be diffusion controlled as the plots of i_d vs $\sqrt{t}$ yielded straight lines passing through the origin. For each polarogram the average value of log plot slope was found to be 20 ± 1 mV indicating reversibility of the electrode process involving three-electron reduction.

Effect of ligand concentration: The half wave potential of Ce(III) shifted to more negative values on gradual increase of the concentration of the ligands under study. The plots of $-E_{1/2}$ against $\log C_x$ (logarithm of the concentration of the ligands)

gave straight lines and segmented lines, indicating the formation of single complex in Ce(III)-benzoate and Ce(III)-protocatechuic systems and plural complex formation in Ce(III)-salicylate system (Fig. 1). The stoichiometry of complexes was found to be [Ce(III)-benzoate]^{1:2}, [Ce(III)-(protocatechuic)₂]^{1:2}, [Ce(III)-(salicylate)]^{1:1} and [Ce(III)-(salicylate)₂]^{1:2}. The values of stability constants were calculated by Lingane method⁶ in case of single

Fig. 1. Plots of $\log C_x$ vs $\Delta E_{1/2}$ for 1m M Ce(III) in 1.0 M KCl + 0.01% gelatin at pH. 3.00 ± 0.02 , for
(A) Ce(III)-benzoate $\odot$
(B) Ce(III)-protocatechuic $\triangle$
(C) Ce(III)-salicylate $\square$

species complex, while Deford-Hume⁷ method was used to calculate the formation constants of step wise complex formation of Ce(III)-salicylate system as tabulated in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF Ce(III) COMPLEXES				
Sl. No.	Complex	Ratio M : L	Stability constant	
			Lingane method	Deford-Hume method
1.	[Ce(III)-benzoate] ^{1:2}	1 : 2	$\log \beta_2 = 4.1$	—
2.	[Ce(III)-(protocatechuic) ₂] ^{1:2}	1 : 2	$\log \beta_2 = 6.28$	—
3.	[Ce(III)-salicylate] ^{1:1}	1 : 1	$\log \beta_1 = 3.6$	3.47
4.	[Ce(III)-(salicylate) ₂] ^{1:2}	1 : 2	$\log \beta_2 = 7.2$	6.98

The stability constants are in agreement with the previously published results of Pr(III) and Nd(III) complexes with benzoic acid, protocatechuic acid and salicylic acid respectively^{1,2}.

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Polarographic Behaviour of Ni(II), Co(II), UO₂(II) and Ge(IV) in Aqueous Mixtures of Propylene Carbonate

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A survey of literature reveals that propylene carbonate, which has a fairly high dielectric constant¹ ($\epsilon_{25^\circ} = 64.92$), is a new solvent in so far as the polarography of inorganic depolarizers in organic solvents is concerned. With this aim in view the polarographic behaviour of Ni(II), Co(II), UO₂(II) and Ge(IV) has been studied in presence of aqueous mixtures of propylene carbonate using 0.1 M NaClO₄ as the supporting electrolyte.

Experimental

Stock solutions of Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, UO₂(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (A. R., B.D.H.) and GeO₂ (Fluka, A. R.) were prepared in conductivity water. The concentration of each of the depolarizers in the final solution to be polarographed was maintained at 1.0×10^{-3} M. NaClO₄ (0.1 M) was used as the supporting electrolyte in all the cases. A manual polarograph (Toshniwal CL 02) in conjunction with a polyflex galvanometer (Toshniwal PL 50) was used. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics (in 0.1 M NaClO₄ in open circuit): $h_{corr} = 72.2$ cm, $t = 3.1$ sec, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.84$ mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/2}. All measurements were made at $25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. Requisite amount of Triton X-100 [$2.0 \times 10^{-3}\%$ in the case of Ni(II) and Co(II) and $1.0 \times 10^{-3}\%$ in the case of UO₂(II) and Ge(IV)] was added to suppress the maxima. Purified nitrogen was used for removing dissolved oxygen. The number of electrons (n) involved in the electrode reduction of each of the depolarizers was determined by millicoulometric² method. n is 2 for Ni(II), 2 for Co(II), 1 for each of the two steps of UO₂(II) and 4 for Ge(IV). Knowing the value of n, the diffusion coefficient (D) of the depolarizers was calculated by Ilkovic equation at different percentages of